

ELECTRON BEAM CURE OF COMPOSITES FOR AEROSPACE STRUCTURES

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SUMMARY: In this study the properties and performance of two electron beam (EB)-cured epoxy resins and their composites are compared with those of 3501-6, a thermally-cured epoxy widely used in aerospace structures. Mechanical performance of the EB-cured materials is significantly reduced under hot/wet conditions, due in part to relatively low glass transition temperatures and the susceptibility of a poor fiber-matrix interfacial bond to degradation under the influence of moisture. Both EB-cured resins undergo additional thermal cure, although this does not appear to adversely affect their performance. While EB cure offers several technical and economic advantages over conventional cure, improvements in materials are required before the full benefits of this process can be realized in aerospace structures.

KEYWORDS: electron beam-cure, epoxy composites, aerospace structures

INTRODUCTION

There are four factors that influence material selection for aerospace structures: weight, performance, the ability to fabricate components and cost. Polymeric composite structures hold an edge over metal structures in weight. Great strides have been made in improving composite performance and durability for specific aerospace environments, and a number of new and innovative processing and fabrication techniques are enabling the fabrication of large, integrated and complex composite structures. The stumbling block, however, toward more widespread composites usage in aerospace structures is their cost. This has spawned many research programs in recent years, such as the U.S. Department of Defense's Composites Affordability Initiative (CAI), aimed at reducing the cost of composite structures. While a reduction in raw material costs will help, innovative design concepts and a reduction in fabrication costs (including labor, tooling, cure, assembly, etc) provide a greater impact on overall costs. Over the years electron beams have been widely used in the coatings industry to cure polymeric coatings. In the last 10 years or so, this technology has been gaining attention for the cure of composite materials, primarily because of the potential for cost savings over conventional cure methods. Most of the research in this field has been conducted at Aerospatiale in France [1,2], at Atomic energy of Canada, Ltd. (AECL) in Manitoba, Canada [3,4], and at the Oak Ridge National Laboratory (ORNL) in Oak Ridge, Tennessee [5].

In the electron beam (EB) cure of composites, high-energy electrons from an accelerator initiate polymerization and crosslinking of the matrix resin. This process requires special resin chemistry. Most commercially-available EB-curable polymers have ethylene unsaturation and cure via a free-radical mechanism. In epoxies this unsaturation may be introduced through

acrylation or methacrylation of the terminal epoxy groups. However, conventional epoxy resins may also be EB-cured through a cationic mechanism, using the appropriate catalyst. For applications requiring a higher use-temperature, bismaleimide resins have been employed, modified with reactive diluents which make the material radiation sensitive. Electron penetration into a composite is directly proportional to the beam energy and inversely proportional to the composite density. A 10 MeV beam, for example, can penetrate about 2.5 cm of typical carbon fiber composite (density 1.5 g/cc) [6]. The beam must also penetrate any vacuum bag or pressure vessel if these are required for manufacturing the part. Products with a thickness greater than the EB penetration limit can be cured with x-rays, which are obtained from the same accelerator by placing a conversion target (such as Ta or W) in the path of the electron beam. Although the penetration limit for x-rays is about four times that for electrons, the time needed for curing may increase by a factor of about 10 to 50 since the absorption coefficients for energy from x-rays are generally lower than those from electrons. To limit the use of x-rays, the highest permissible energy level is selected - 10 MeV - above which there is a risk of activating metallic materials. The highest possible power is also used to minimize cure time.

EB-cure of composite structures offers a number of advantages over traditional autoclave cure:

- Selectable-temperature curing. Cure at ambient temperature allows the use of inexpensive tooling, while cure at the service temperature of the finished part reduces thermal residual stresses during its use. There is a temperature rise during cure, due to exothermic reactions and absorbed radiation energy; however, excessive heating can be avoided by using multiple passes to deliver the required dose.
- Reduced cure time. A 50-kW accelerator can cure about 1200 kg of composites per hour [7]. This is several times faster than conventional thermal cure in an autoclave, even though composite components are cured in batches as opposed to one at a time with EB cure.
- Improved material handling, EB-cure resins may be stored under ambient conditions and have longer shelf life than thermal-cure formulations. EB processing is a continuous operation, and components may be individually cured immediately after assembly, facilitating production scheduling and inventory control.
- Reduced solvent usage and volatile generation.
- Controllable energy input (and lower consumption) with minimal waste. Comparisons of energy required to cure specific composite parts ranging in mass from 0.3 to 16 kg showed a 10 times lower energy requirement for EB cure compared to autoclave cure [8].
- Greater design flexibility. This process allows the cure of selected areas only, the co-cure of different matrix materials, fabrication of unsymmetric and unbalanced composites, uniform cure of a range of thicknesses in the same part, and incorporation of metal inserts and fixtures prior to cure.

All these attractive features combine to create a process which is inherently less expensive than autoclave cure, particularly when high throughput is required. In addition EB cure could be a potentially enabling technology for the fabrication of very large structures such as cryogenic fuel tanks and for the processing of critical composite space structures, where reduced thermal stresses are essential for dimensional stability in the space environment. Several feasibility studies have been conducted which demonstrate the inherent economic and technical advantages offered by EB cure for aerospace composite structures; however, the success of this technology is dependent on development of the appropriate material systems and processes. When selecting a material system for a particular application, certain property

tradeoffs are necessary. For example, improved toughness is usually achieved at the expense of reduced elevated temperature performance. Keying on improvements in one property (such as glass transition temperature) as a measure of success or maturity of this technology is therefore inappropriate. A better assessment of the state of the art is obtained by selecting one or more specific structural applications and evaluating how EB-cured candidate systems meet their property/performance requirements. Alternatively, the characteristics of state-of-the-art EB-cured material systems may be directly compared with a baseline thermally-cured system already in use in aerospace structures. This last approach was the one employed in the present study to assess the status of EB-cured materials systems for aircraft and spacecraft structures.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

Two state-of-the art EB-cured material systems were evaluated, RB-47 (from Aerospatiale) and CAT-B (from Applied Poleramics, Inc.), representative of free-radical and cationic curing mechanisms, respectively. RB-47 is a methacrylated epoxy resin while CAT-B is a mixture of epoxies derived from diglycidyl ether of bisphenol-A and cured with a photoinitiator. The baseline for comparison was 3501-6 (Hercules, Inc), the thermally-cured epoxy workhorse of the aerospace industry. Composites of these resins reinforced with AS4 (unsized) and IM7 carbon fibers were also evaluated.

Processing

Both RB-47 and CAT-B were obtained as EB-cured neat resin plates for evaluation. Neat 3501-6 epoxy was fabricated into a plaque by casting the debulked molten resin between glass plates at 121°C followed by two hours at 177°C. Unidirectional AS4/CAT-B hot-melt prepreg tape was fabricated on a drum winder. A minimum resin bath temperature of 120°C was required to obtain adequate resin viscosity and tow impregnation. The prepreg was cut and layed up into laminates of $[0]_8$, $[\pm 45]_{2s}$ and $[0_2/90_2]_T$ orientations. These lay-ups were consolidated in a vacuum bag for eight hours at 70°C, and then EB-cured at Electron Beam Services, Inc. while still under vacuum. The cure was accomplished with a dose of 200 kGy delivered in four passes of the composite under the electron beam. An EB-cured $[0]_8$ panel of IM7/RB-47 was also obtained for evaluation.

Characterization

Moisture absorption of the cured neat resins was characterized after immersion in distilled water at 23°C. Thermal expansion measurements were made over the range of -100°C or 100°C using bonded strain gages. Thermal analysis was conducted on TA Instruments equipment with DSC and TGA scans (in air and nitrogen) at rates of 10°C/min. Dynamic mechanical analysis was performed on a Rheometrics RDS-II dynamic mechanical analyzer in the torsion mode at a frequency of 100rad/s and a scan rate of 5°C/min. All glass transition temperatures (T_g) reported in this paper were determined from the knee in the storage modulus curve. Isothermal aging studies were also conducted in the RDS-II (in nitrogen) in which the dynamic storage modulus was continuously monitored as a function of aging time.

Mechanical characterization of resin and composite specimens was conducted at MTS test machines. The majority of specimens were tested dry at 23°C(RTD), dry at 121°C(ETD), and wet at either 23°C(RTW) or 121°C (ETW) after boiling in water for 24 hours. Fracture toughness of the neat resins was determined under ambient conditions, after drying in a vacuum oven at 50°C and after aging at 121°C in a vacuum for 72 hours.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Feasibility studies have indicated that electron beam cure of composites has some compelling economic and technical advantages over traditional thermal cure in an autoclave and is also an enabling technology for certain integrated structural designs. materials development, however, has not kept pace with improvements in hardware and process technology. A composite material system must meet some minimum mechanical property requirements under a range of test conditions to be considered for aircraft structural applications. a generic set of such tests was conducted to compare the EB-cure material systems with a baseline thermally-cured system accepted for such applications. The candidate material systems selected for this study represent the current state of the art with respect to the two major categories of EB-cure epoxies (free radical cure and cationic cure) although they are not necessarily optimized for the tests to which they were subjected. The ability to cure at ambient temperature, with consequent reduction in thermal residual stresses, makes EB-cure technology attractive for composite space structures. A key requirement for a space structure is dimensional stability over the range of operational temperatures. While it is advocated that thermal postcure of EB-cured composites (for cationically-cured systems) may be unnecessary [5], these structures will nevertheless experience elevated temperature at the upper extreme of the thermal cycles, and it is of interest to determine if the inevitable thermal postcure results in structural distortion.

Characterization of Neat Resins

Moisture absorption in the cured neat resins as a function of time is shown in Figure 1. While the initial rates of absorption for RB-47 and 3501-6 are similar, they begin to diverge after 1600 hours. Compared to these resins, moisture is absorbed at a slower rate in CAT-B. From the trends displayed to date, it appears that the thermally-cured 3501-6 will have a higher equilibrium moisture content than either of the EB-cured resins. Thermogravimetric analyses, conducted in both nitrogen and air, display excellent thermal and thermooxidative stability for all three resins up to 300°C. While the rate of mass loss from 3501-6 increases sharply at about 310°C (in nitrogen), the EB-cured resins are stable up to about 380°C. At 400°C the 3501-6 epoxy retains 74% of its weight in air and 67% of its weight in nitrogen, compared to 87% and 89%, respectively, for the EB-cured resins. Thermal expansions of the EB-cured resins over the range of -100°C to 100°C are essentially the same. The average coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) over this range is about 20% higher for the EB-cured resins (51 ppm/°C) compared to 3501-6 (41 ppm/°C). This translates to an approximately 10% higher transverse CTE in a unidirectional ply reinforced with AS4 fiber with a fiber volume fraction of 0.6.

From a DSC scan of the EB-cured CAT-B resin (Figure 2A), there appears to be residual uncured material in the sample. Taking the ratio of the corresponding exotherm (11.5 mcal/mg) to that generated from the thermal cure of uncured liquid resin (106.6 mcal/mg) to that generated from the thermal cure of uncured liquid resin (106.6 mcal/mg), the degree of

cure of the EB-cured CAT-B panel is estimated at 89%. This is surprising, considering that an electron beam dose of 300 kGy was employed for this cure, in excess of the standard dose of 150 kGy. In comparison, the 3501-6 plaque, fabricated in-house, has a degree of cure of 97%. From a DSC scan of the EB-cured RB-47, it is unclear if there is any exotherm generated due to the uncertainty in establishing a baseline for the scan. However, when a sample of the same material is thermally postcured and then scanned in the DSC, comparison with the initial scan (Figure 2B) clearly shows that the resin cure in the original plaque was incomplete. Uncured resin, to quantify the degree of cure of the RB-47 plaque, was unavailable. From these results it appears that the application of thermal energy to an EB-cured epoxy is capable of generating exotherm through some additional chemical reaction which does not occur under electron beam irradiation. When EB-cured composites are employed in service, elevated temperature exposure may trigger such (thermally-induced) reactions, with consequent changes in shape, properties or performance of the structure.

Representative dynamic storage moduli (G') of the three resins as functions of temperature are shown in Figure 3. From this figure it can be seen that RB-47 has a relatively low T_g (115°C). The storage modulus of CAT-B starts to drop at about 110°C. However, simultaneous thermal postcure limits the rate of decline in G' until the second knee (at about 160°C), giving rise to a T_g of 160°C. The storage modulus curve for 3501-6 is relatively flat on this log scale, with a sharp knee and a corresponding T_g of 202°C. A better representation of this data is a plot of retention of storage modulus (on a linear scale) as a function of temperature, as shown in Figure 4, which allows direct comparison of the three resins. For example, RB-47, CAT-B and 3501-6 show a retention of 60% of their room-temperature storage moduli at temperatures of approximately 108°C, 133°C and 185°C, respectively; alternatively, at 121°C, RB-47, CAT-B and 3501-6 retain 42, 70 and 82%, respectively, of their storage moduli at room temperature. These data demonstrate the superiority of thermally-cured 3501-6 for elevated-temperature applications.

Tensile properties of the neat resins were determined under ambient conditions (RTD), at 121°C (ETD), and at room temperature after boiling in water for 24 hours (RTW). As expected from the poor retention of storage modulus under dynamic mechanical testing, both the EB-cured resins experience a knockdown in tensile modulus at 121°C (Figure 5), the RB-47 more so than the CAT-B, while 3501-6 retains about 75% of its room-temperature modulus.

Resin tensile strength at 121°C follows the same trend as tensile modulus (Figure 6), with strength retention of only about 25% and 55% of the corresponding room-temperature values for RB-47 and CAT-B, respectively. Absorbed moisture causes only a 15-20% drop in tensile modulus of the EB-cured resins, although the corresponding drop in tensile strength is close to 40%. Thermally-cured 3501-6, on the other hand, suffers only a 5% loss in modulus under similar conditions and a 25% loss in strength.

Composite Processing

Unitape prepreg was processed in-house on a drum winder using unsized AS4 (12K0 fiber and CAT-B resin. This resin may be processed from the melt or from a solution in methylethyl ketone. The former option was preferred, to eliminate the necessity of having to remove residual solvent prior to cure. The minimum melt temperature for satisfactory fiber tow impregnation was found to be 120°C. Cure of this cationically-cured resin system is advanced thermally, however, which limits the resin pot life. Cure advancement at elevated

temperatures is illustrated in Figure 7, where the dynamic viscosity of the resin at four different temperatures is plotted as a function of time. It is apparent that at a processing temperature of 125°C, the limited pot life of the resin requires that prepregging be completed in three hours.

The processing challenge with EB-cured materials lies in obtaining a void-free part through appropriate consolidation *prior* to cure, since the resin is immobile *during* cure. The consolidation temperature has to be carefully selected; it must be high enough to significantly reduce resin viscosity, thereby allowing compaction and the escape of trapped air, but not too high to significantly advance the thermal cure of the resin. Initially, panels were consolidated in a vacuum bag at 70°C cooled to ambient temperature, and the vacuum released prior to cure in the electron beam. This resulted in panels with large unbonded areas between plies. In the second attempt the vacuum was maintained during the electron beam cure. A vacuum bag tends to retain the heat from absorbed energy and cure reactions, resulting in an increase in panel temperature during cure. The temperature rise was limited to 50°C by delivering the required dose in four passes. Ultrasonic C-scans of the resulting panels revealed mixed results; some panels appeared to be well-consolidated, while others in the same batch were not. Only the well-consolidated panels were tested. These preliminary results indicate the need for some consolidation pressure during EB-cure and further optimization of the consolidation conditions prior to cure.

Composite Characterization

In addition to the test conditions used for neat resins, the mechanical properties of composites were also evaluated under hot/wet conditions. The results are summarized in Table 1. The longitudinal tensile modulus of IM7/RB-47 approximates the value predicted from the rule of mixtures, although the tensile strength is substantially lower than expected. The low tensile strength is due to premature longitudinal splitting of the specimen originating at the gripped ends which, in turn, arises from poor fiber-matrix bond strength. This is borne out by the relatively low 90° tensile strength for this composite system. Reduction in matrix strength at elevated temperature causes a 50% drop in 90° tensile strength. After boiling in water for 24 hours, there is a 65% drop in 90° tensile strength at ambient temperature. From a comparison with the trends observed in neat RB-47, it appears that the water boil causes a significant deterioration in the already low fiber-matrix bond strength of this composite system. This was confirmed from SEM examinations of the fracture surfaces of failed test specimens. A combination of moisture *and* elevated temperature (121°C) drastically reduces the transverse strength to a value which is less than 10% of the dry, room-temperature strength. A similar trend was observed in interlaminar shear strength measurements. Corresponding manufacturer's data for a thermally-cured IM7/epoxy composite system (IM7/8552) are also shown in the table for comparison.

Matrix-dominated properties of the AS4/CAT-B composite system are compared to those of thermally-cured AS4/3501-6 in Table 1. There is a greater drop in the in-plane shear modulus of AS4/CAT-B at 121°C (35%, compared to 15% for AS4/3501-6), while the reduction after the 24-hour water boil is 23% (compared to only 5% for AS4/3501-6). The thermally-cured composite displays fairly good retention of matrix- and interface-dominated properties, such as transverse tensile and flexural strength, at elevated temperature and under the influence of absorbed moisture. On the other hand, AS4/CAT-B displays a 23% drop in 90° flexural strength at 121°C and a 42% drop at room temperature after boiling in water for 24 hours,

suggesting significant moisture-induced deterioration of the fiber-matrix interface. This was confirmed from SEM examinations of failed test specimens.

Isothermal Aging of Resins and Composites

A possible application of EB-cure technology is in space structures, because of the potential of greatly reduced residual stresses (and hence better dimensional stability) resulting from ambient curing conditions. However, the lack of full cure in an electron beam (as evidenced from the DSC studies described earlier) raises a concern about the potential for dimensional distortion when cure advances (thermally) in the application environment. Space structures may cycle between -157°C and 121°C . Consequently, neat resin and composite specimens were isothermally aged at 121°C to simulate the upper temperature of such a space environment. The changes in dynamic storage moduli of EB-cured neat resins and composites with time are shown in Figures 8 and 9, respectively. Most of the change in storage modulus occurs within the first 10 hours of aging. dynamic storage moduli vs. temperature of EB-cured composites are compared before and after isothermal aging (for 48 hours) in Figure 10. The two knees in the baseline curve for CAT-B are more pronounced here than in the corresponding G' curve for the neat resin (Figure 3). The first knee occurs at approximately 60°C , which is the temperature at which the exotherm initiates during the DSC scan (Figure 2A). The disappearance of this knee after gain (Figure 10) suggests that it arises from additional cure during the test and not from a second toughening phase of lower T_g . The change in composite T_g with aging is more pronounced than the corresponding change in neat resin T_g , as seen from Table 2.

Possible consequences of thermal postcure and the increase in stiffness which occur during aging are a decrease in fracture toughness and an increase in residual stresses. The extent of warpage of an unsymmetrical laminate provides a measure of the built-in residual stresses. A $[0_4/90_4]_T$ unsymmetric laminate of AS4/CAT-B was fabricated, and narrow strips, 15 cm long and 6.35 mm wide, were sectioned. This narrow width limits the warpage to a single direction. Chemical shrinkage during cure resulted in a slight curvature of the strips under ambient conditions (0.7 mm, compared to 9.7 mm for a thermally-cured AS4/3501-6 laminate with the same layout). On heating, thermal expansion causes the strips to straighten out and then experience a reversal in curvature which increases out to 121°C . With the temperature maintained at 121°C , however, there is no further change in warpage (determined by monitoring the central deflection of the composite strip to the nearest 0.05 mm) over a 48-hour period, indicating no measurable increase in residual stresses with this isothermal aging. The fracture toughness of neat resin specimens aged for 72 hours at 121°C was also measured and compared with the corresponding values for unaged specimens. The results are shown in Table 2. Fracture toughness does not decrease with aging; in fact it appears to increase, possibly due to further (thermal) advancement of cure. Preliminary indications, therefore, are that the (thermal) cure advancement seen in DSC studies does not adversely affect the performance of EB-cured composites.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

Electron beam cure offers significant technical and economic advantages over conventional autoclave cure of composite structures for aerospace applications. The key to realizing the potential of this technology is development of the appropriate composite constituents (matrix resins, fiber sizings) which will yield a cured product equivalent or superior to its thermally-

cured counterpart. The two EB-cured systems evaluated in this study (epoxy-based RB-47 and CAT-B) both display evidence of additional thermal cure, in spite of receiving an electron dose greater than that normally employed. This suggests the possibility of thermally-activated chemical reactions occurring in the composite structure in its application environment. However, sustained exposure to a temperature of 121°C reveals no adverse aging effects; there is no measurable increase in residual stress and no deterioration in resin toughness, although the dynamic storage modulus and T_g increase slightly. Cured resin thermal and thermooxidative stabilities are on par with those of thermally-cured 3501-6 epoxy; however, resin T_g is significantly lower, which translates to a significant to substantial reduction in mechanical performance at elevated temperatures. This poor performance at elevated temperature carries over to the composite and is compounded by the susceptibility of a relatively weak fiber-matrix interfacial bond to degradation in the presence of moisture. A first step toward reaping the benefits of this process in aerospace structures is to develop resin formulation with inherently high T_g and appropriate fiber sizings that will generate acceptable hot/wet mechanical properties.

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